

nature. The magnetic moment values^{3,4} of all the complexes were in the normal range. The values for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes correspond that for high-spin octahedral complexes.

The infrared spectra of the free ligand (*o*-EMBH) exhibit band at 3 180 cm⁻¹ due to OH of carboxylic group⁵. This band however disappeared in all the complexes. The absorption at 2 570 cm⁻¹ is assigned⁶ to ν_{COOH} in the free ligand. This band is also not observed in the spectra of the complexes. These data supports the presence of deprotonated carboxylic group in the complexes⁷. The ligand (*o*-EMBH) absorbs at 1 210 and 685 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned^{8,9} to $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S-R}}$, respectively. However, $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ band is observed at 1 185 – 1 195 cm⁻¹ in all complexes, which shows coordination through hydroxylic oxygen of carboxylic group. The $\nu_{\text{C-S-R}}$ band is also not observed in the spectra of the complexes, which shows that sulphur is coordinating in all the complexes. The coordination of water molecule in the complexes Sl. nos. 1, 4, 7, 10 (Table 1) was evident by the appearance of a broad hump at 3 450 cm⁻¹. The appearance of a band at 230–280 cm⁻¹ confirms the coordination of nitrogen of pyridine or α -picolin in the complexes. The coordination through oxygen and sulphur was further supported by the appearance of $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ band at 600–625 and 325–340 cm⁻¹, respectively.

The electronic spectra of the mixed-ligand Mn^{II} complexes exhibit three bands of low extinction coefficient at 16 500–17 000, 26 400–27 150 and 28 800–29 000 cm⁻¹ due to transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ (ν_1), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ (ν_2) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_{1g}(G)$ (ν_3), respectively. Here all the transitions are weak as they are spin-forbidden. The 10 *Dq* (10 300–10 400 cm⁻¹), *B'* (600–650 cm⁻¹) and *B* (0.62–0.67) values are within the range of the values for octahedral Mn^{II} complexes. The mixed ligand Co^{II} complexes exhibit three bands at 8 500–8 700, 16 400–17 400 and 20 800–21 100 cm⁻¹ due to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. The 10 *Dq* (8 591–9 113.5 cm⁻¹), *B'* (781–825.5 cm⁻¹) and *B* (0.697–0.739) values are quite consistent with the values reported for octahedral structure. The mixed-ligand complexes of Ni^{II} also exhibit three bands at 10 100–10 400, 16 000–16 950 and 25 500–28 400 cm⁻¹ due to transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. The 10 *Dq* (10 110–10 330 cm⁻¹), *B'* (777–939 cm⁻¹) and *B* (0.74–0.90) values are consistent with the values reported for octahedral structure.

The visible spectra of Cu^{II} complexes exhibit broad asymmetric band at 12 300–14 875 cm⁻¹. In the case of mixed-ligand complexes of Cu^{II}, all the six ligands are not the same. Hence, crystal field of such complexes are tetragonally distorted and it becomes of *D_{4h}* symmetry as such. Consequently, two degenerate states, *i.e.* 2E_g and ${}^2T_{2g}$ further split up into two components each. Thus three bands at 12 300–14 850, 12 500–14 875 and

12 600–14 875 cm⁻¹ correspond to transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}(\nu_1)$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g(\nu_3)$, respectively. But due to small energy gap between these components, all the three bands envelop together and a broad symmetrical band is observed. These values are in good agreement with the values reported for distorted octahedral complexes of copper(II).

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Polarographic Studies on Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cadmium(II) with Picolines and Carboxylate Ions

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GAUR and Sharma¹ studied polarographically the simple complexes of Cd^{II} with β - and γ -picolines at 30° and concluded that Cd^{II} forms two successive complexes (1 : 1 and 1 : 2) with β -picoline with stability constants, 18.5 \pm 2 and 224 \pm 5 and with γ -picoline three complexes (1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3) with stability constants 33 \pm 3, 31 \pm 5 and 665 \pm 10. However, in these studies no mention has been made as to the pH at which the study was made as many changes² in a system of complexes may occur when the pH of the solution is changed. A survey of literature³⁻¹⁸ reveals that simple complexes of Cd^{II} with a number of carboxylate ions, such as formate, oxalate, tartrate, succinate, citrate, malonate and maleate have been studied polarographically. However, the mixed complexes of Cd^{II} with these acids and picolines have not been studied so far. The present study therefore seeks to undertake comprehensive polarographic studies on the mixed complexes of Cd^{II} with β - and γ -picolines, and some carboxylate ions, *viz.* oxalate, malonate, succinate and tartrate.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade, and their stock solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The concentrations of Cd^{II} (from CdCl₂) was maintained at $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$. Potassium salts of oxalic, succinic, tartaric and malonic acids were used as the source of oxalate (Ox²⁻), succinate (Succ²⁻) and malonate (Mal²⁻) ions. Sodium potassium tartrate was used as a source of tartrate (Tart²⁻) ions. NaNO₃ was used as a supporting electrolyte and also to maintain a constant ionic strength ($\mu=2.0$). As no polarographic maximum appeared in the present study, addition of Tritonx-100 as suppressor was avoided. Polarograms of the solutions were obtained by means of a Toshniwal CL 02B digital polarograph. Purified hydrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The measurements were made at a constant temperature ($25 \pm 0.1^\circ$). The number of electrons (n) involved in the polarographic reduction of Cd^{II} in presence of ligands was determined by the millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon¹⁴. This gave the value of n equal to 2 in each case. The value of D , the diffusion-coefficient of Cd^{II} in presence of increasing concentrations of the ligands was obtained from Ilkovic equation. The current at the end of the drop (*i.e.* the maximum current) was noted in each case. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics in 2.0 M NaNO₃, open circuit: $m=3.70 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t=3.2 \text{ s}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}=2.90 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$, $h_{\text{corr}}=37.5 \text{ cm}$.

Results and Discussion

Cd^{II} yields well defined reduction waves in the presence of increasing amounts of β - and γ -picolines (hereafter represented as β -pico, and γ -pico) and oxalate (Ox²⁻), malonate (Mal²⁻), succinate (Succ²⁻) and tartrate (Tart²⁻) ions. In each case, the polarographic waves are well defined and diffusion-controlled as the plots of i_d vs $h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$ are linear and pass through the origin. The slope values of log-plots line in the range 30–32 mV at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. These are in close agreement, within the experimental error, with the theoretical value (29.6 mV at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$) for a 2-electron reduction process thereby showing¹⁵ that the polarographic reduction of Cd^{II} in the presence of different ligands is reversible.

Composition and stability constant of simple complexes of Cd^{II} with β - and γ -picolines and carboxylate ions: The composition and stability constants of simple complexes of Cd^{II} with β - and γ -pico, Ox²⁻, Mal²⁻, Succ²⁻ and Tart²⁻ were determined separately prior to the study of the mixed systems. Identical conditions were maintained in both the simple and the mixed systems. With the addition of increasing amounts of picolines or carboxylate ions, $E_{1/2}$ of Cd^{II} is shifted to more negative potentials thereby showing the complex formation. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs log [Tart²⁻] is straight line. This shows the formation of a single

complex. However, the plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs log [Ox²⁻], log [Succ²⁻], log [Mal²⁻], log [(β -pico)] and log [(γ -pico)] are smooth curves, thereby showing the formation of successive complexes. The composition and stability constants of the former systems have been determined by Lingane¹⁶ method, while that of the latter by DeFord and Humes method¹⁷. The composition and stability constants of various single ligand complex species have been summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SIMPLE AND MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF Cd^{II} AT $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

System	Composition	Stability constant
Cd ^{II} - Ox ²⁻	[Cd(Ox)]	log $\beta_1 = 2.9$
	[Cd(Ox) ₂] ²⁻	log $\beta_2 = 4.0$
Cd ^{II} - Succ ²⁻	[Cd(Succ)]	log $\beta_1 = 4.9$
	[Cd(Succ) ₂] ²⁻	log $\beta_2 = 1.94$
Cd ^{II} - Mal ²⁻	[Cd(Mal)]	log $\beta_1 = 2.04$
	[Cd(Mal) ₂] ²⁻	log $\beta_2 = 3.04$
Cd ^{II} - Tart ²⁻	[Cd(Tart)]	log $\beta_1 = 1.7$
	[Cd(Tart) ₂] ²⁻	log $\beta_2 = 2.3$
Cd ^{II} - β -pico	[Cd(β -pico)]	log $\beta_1 = 3.48$
	[Cd(β -pico) ₂] ²⁻	log $\beta_2 = 2.84$
Cd ^{II} - γ -pico	[Cd(γ -pico)]	log $\beta_1 = 1.2$
	[Cd(γ -pico) ₂] ²⁻	log $\beta_2 = 2.0$
Cd ^{II} - Succ ²⁻ - β -pico	[Cd(β -pico) ₂] ²⁻	log $\beta_2 = 3.42$
	[Cd(γ -pico) ₂] ²⁻	log $\beta_2 = 1.30$
Cd ^{II} - Tart ²⁻ - β -pico	[Cd(γ -pico) ₂] ²⁻	log $\beta_2 = 2.48$
	[Cd(γ -pico) ₂] ²⁻	log $\beta_2 = 3.28$
Cd ^{II} - Ox ²⁻ - γ -pico	[Cd(Succ)(β -pico)]	log $\beta_{12} = 4.00$
	[Cd(Succ) ₂ (β -pico)] ²⁻	log $\beta_{12} = 3.22$
Cd ^{II} - Succ ²⁻ - γ -pico	[Cd(Tart)(β -pico)]	log $\beta_{12} = 3.10$
	[Cd(Ox)(γ -pico)]	log $\beta_{12} = 4.72$
Cd ^{II} - Mal ²⁻ - γ -pico	[Cd(β -pico) ₂] ²⁻	log $\beta_{12} = 5.24$
	[Cd(Succ)(γ -pico)]	log $\beta_{12} = 3.00$
Cd ^{II} - Tart ²⁻ - γ -pico	[Cd(Succ)(γ -pico)]	log $\beta_{12} = 3.61$
	[Cd(Succ) ₂ (γ -pico)] ²⁻	log $\beta_{12} = 3.47$
Cd ^{II} - Ox ²⁻ - β -pico	[Cd(Tart)(γ -pico)]	log $\beta_{12} = 3.0$
	[Cd(Mal)(γ -pico)]	log $\beta_{12} = 3.24$
Cd ^{II} - Succ ²⁻ - β -pico	[Cd(Mal)(γ -pico)]	log $\beta_{12} = 3.88$
	[Cd(Mal) ₂ (γ -pico)] ²⁻	log $\beta_{12} = 3.81$

Composition and stability constants of mixed systems: These were determined by Schaap and McMasters¹⁸ method. The concentration of carboxylate ion was varied, keeping [pico] constant. In each case, $E_{1/2}$ values were found to be more negative than those obtained in the case of binary systems, thereby showing the formation of mixed complexes. The polarographic characteristics and F_{ij} [X,Y] functions for the mixed ligand systems have been determined and from the analysis of these functions, the values of constants A , B , C , etc. have been computed. From the values of these constants, the composition and stability constants of various mixed complex species have been determined (Table 1).

Comparative stabilities of mixed-ligand and simple complexes: The stabilities of mixed-ligand (ternary) and simple (binary) complexes have been compared in terms of mixing constant (log K_M values) and disproportionation constant (log X values). The results are summarised below.

Mixing equilibria: The log K_M values for the following mixing equilibria 1–5:

work out to be 0.68, 1.48, 0.73, 0.34 and 0.85, respectively. In each case, a positive value of log K_M shows that the mixed complexes formed in equilibria (1)–(5) are more stable than the corresponding simple complexes.

Disproportionation equilibria: The following disproportionation equilibria (1–12) are involved in the various ternary systems,

The log X values for the equilibria (1)–(12) are –2.54, –1.4, –1.36, –2.96, –3.10, –1.46, –1.90, –1.42, –0.68, –1.7, –2.18, and –1.66, respectively. In each case, a negative value of log X shows that the mixed complexes are more stable than the corresponding binary complexes.

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On the Linear Free Energy Relationship

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THE importance and utility of the Hammett and Taft equations are well known¹⁻³. For the reactions of the type

We have $\log K = \log \frac{K_{\text{HA}}}{K_{\text{HR}}} = \rho\sigma$ (Hammett equation)

where HR=reference acid, HA=substituted acid ρ , known as the reaction solvent parameter at a particular temperature, measures the sensitivity of the reaction to electron supply or withdrawal, whereas σ , known as the substituent constant, measures the ability of the substituent to supply or withdraw electrons, σ is apparently independent of reaction, solvent and temperature⁴.

The extra-thermodynamic model proposed by Hepler and Hara^{5,6} shows clearly that the Hammett (or Taft) equation is more general than it ought to be. The thermodynamic functions have been written in terms of internal (intrinsic to the molecules and ions of the acid and base) and external or environmental (resulting from the interaction of the acid and base with the solvents) effects. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \Delta H^\circ &= \delta \Delta H_{\text{ext}} + \delta \Delta H_{\text{int}} \\ \text{and } \delta \Delta S^\circ &= \delta \Delta S_{\text{ext}} + \delta \Delta S_{\text{int}} \approx \delta \Delta S_{\text{ext}} \end{aligned}$$